

READOLOGY: A POLYHEDRAL APPROACH IN ENHANCING LITERACY AMONG NON-READERS IN BUAYA- BUAYA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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READology: A Polyhedral Approach in Enhancing Literacy among Non-Readers in Buaya- Buaya Elementary School

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Abstract

Teaching students to read while between school and home study has rendered schools more vulnerable to the pandemic. In support of the MBHTE's 5 Bs, an innovative, evidence-based, and comprehensive approach to improve K-4 learners' literacy and numeracy skills and socio-emotional well-being that anchored on Department Order No. 70, s. 2011 known as Every Child a Reader Program, the Division Memorandum No. 149, s. 2022 stated the conduct of the Division-Wide Literacy and Numeracy Pre-Assessment for School Year 2022-2023. It examined how READology: A Polyhedral Approach Improved Literacy for Buaya-Buaya Elementary School Non-Readers. Researchers tested if this method improved student reading. Research covered the first 2022-2023 semester. The 198 responders were Grades 1–3. It used quantitative and qualitative methods. The CRLA-BoSY (Pre-test) and CRLA-MoSY (Post-test) checklist gathered study outcomes. Gains Analysis analyzed results. Moderate refreshers up to Grade Ready increased, while full refreshers dropped substantially. Full Refresher decreased 67 (34%) Magindanawn, 44 (36%) Filipino, and 20 (31%) English. For Moderate Refresher, there are 4 (2%) gain in Magindanawn, 2 (2%) in Filipino, and 4 (6%) in English. CRLA-MoSY (Post-test) rises suggested respondents improved. The CRLA-BoSY (Pre-test) and CRLA-MoSY (Post-test) differences show READology Approach enhanced learner's reading. The qualitative results showed that READology simplifies reading, provides letter names and sounds, boosts confidence, creates an efficient Game-Based learning environment, helps develop reading and writing skills through visuals, and fosters care and compassion between learners and their parents.

Keywords: *READology, polyhedral, literacy, non-readers, Philippines*

Introduction

Literacy is a fundamental skill that plays a crucial role in an individual's personal, educational, and professional development. One of the essential components of literacy is reading, as it allows individuals to access information, broaden their knowledge base, and enhance their critical thinking skills (Saefullah, 2022). As indicated in the Division Memorandum No. 149, s. 2022 stated the conduct of the Division-Wide Literacy and Numeracy Pre-Assessment for School Year 2022-2023 in support of the MBHTE's 5 Bs which is an innovative, evidence-based, and comprehensive approach to improve K-4 Learners' literacy and Numeracy skills and socio-emotional well-being that anchored on Department Order No. 70, s. 2011 known as Every Child a Reader Program which aims to make the Filipino learners a generation of readers.

It is critical to provide mistake correction for pupils in order to promote effective word reading skills and phrasing that will help in text comprehension (Endo, 2022). The worldwide health crisis has presented unique hurdles to literacy development, especially among non-readers. Educators play a critical role in molding students' reading habits. In order to accomplish this endeavor successfully, one must possess the necessary expertise. Gaining support and encouragement from others will significantly aid in achieving the intended goal. Educators have a critical responsibility to guide young learners through the acquisition of linguistic precision, the development of fluency, and the precise articulation of words. Students are provided with the opportunity to receive professional guidance in assessing their reading proficiency and choosing suitable materials that correspond to their age, cognitive capabilities, and time constraints (Jose, 2011).

However, in Buaya-Buaya Elementary School, there is a significant number of non-readers who struggle with literacy. These non-readers face challenges in understanding the essence and meaning of the books they read. To address this issue, an action research project entitled "READology: A Polyhedral Approach in Enhancing Literacy among Non-Readers" has been developed. It explores diverse techniques to engage and empower non-readers and emphasizes literacy's many features and dimensions, understanding that literacy improvement needs a comprehensive and adaptive approach. It draws inspiration from the School Reading Coordinator, which is an initiative by the researchers to improve reading skills through various activities. The project recognizes the importance of early intervention and aims to bridge the gap between learner's experiences with books at home and reading instruction at school.

This study seeks to detect literacy gaps and contribute to the conversation on educational resilience in the face of extraordinary challenges. This promotes a more inclusive and resilient literacy education paradigm by providing practical insights, techniques, and interventions that may be applied to comparable educational environments. This study aims to improve literacy teaching using READology, giving non-readers of Buaya-Buaya Elementary School and beyond a better future.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine how READology as an approach addresses the reading difficulties experienced by Buaya-Buaya Grade

1 to 3 of struggling readers. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the reading performance of learners before the implementation of READology as an approach response to reading difficulties?
2. What is the reading performance of learners after the implementation of READology as an approach response to reading difficulties?
3. What is the difference in the performance of the learners before and after the implementation of READology as an approach response to reading difficulties?
4. How does READology as an approach address the reading difficulties experience by the learners?

Innovation, Intervention and Strategy

1. The ELKONIN Box – let the non-readers improve their ability to read and spell by encouraging them to actively interact with the process of decoding and mixing sounds. This tool is for helping non-readers break words down into their constituent sounds. Since the researchers wanted the non-readers to focus on phonemic sounds instead of letters to begin with, by using of the boxes with pictures first. This start with words that made up of two or three sounds, then move on to longer ones. Start with words that have simple phonemes instead of blends. Start with pictures instead of printed words. Emphasize the beginning, middle, and end sounds

2. The MARUNGKO APPROACH – this technique is beneficial for non-readers since it departs from the conventional phonetic approach and uses a more all-encompassing approach to teaching reading and writing. Non-readers can begin to build the necessary skills to decode and read unfamiliar printed words by grasping basic sound-letter relationships and supporting their transition into learning to read, such as identifying syllables, blending sounds, and recognizing beginning and end sounds in words. Using this approach is finding patterns of rhyme, initial/final sound, onset/rime, consonants and vowels, by: Matching pictures to other pictures, Matching pictures to sound-letter patterns (graphemes), Matching pictures to words, Matching words to other words, using games to practice the awareness of syllables, rhyme, initial/final sound, and individual sounds in words.

3. The CLAVERIA TECHNIQUE – this is use to familiar visuals of the syllables to help teacher capture their students' attention quickly. This is to teach the non-reader by giving them hint of the start of the first letter sound of the word by giving them and showing picture which is related and has a starting letter sound to have a clue how to read the given word correctly.

Methodology

Research Design

This action research utilized a combination of quantitative and qualitative designs particularly using descriptive and thematic analyses. In the quantitative portion, pre and post-tests were used while in the qualitative section, the narrative interview was conducted. Both of these were utilized to determine the effect of READology as an approach response to the reading difficulties experienced by the non-readers.

The one group pre-test and post-test was used to determine the effect of using READology as an intervention in the reading difficulties of the Grade One to Grade Three Non-readers. In this design, all participants were given the same treatment and assessment.

The narrative interview was conducted to allow the participants to narrate their experiences and get a finer description on how READology as an approach responded to the reading difficulties they experienced.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were One Hundred Ninety-Eight (198) Non-readers from Grade One to Grade Three. They were chosen to participate because the researchers found out that these learners were lagging behind due to difficulties in reading based on the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA) result.

Procedure

The researchers used instruments to determine the effect of READology approach as response to reading difficulties of the Non-readers.

The CRLA-BoSY (Pre-test) and CRLA-MoSY (Post-test) were designed to determine the significant gains from the intervention used in this study. This instrument showed the reading performance of the learners during the CRLA-BoSY (Pre-test) and CRLA-MoSY (Post-test) how the intervention improves the reading abilities, while the Interview Guide Questionnaire was designed to describe how the intervention improves the reading abilities of the Non-readers.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using the Analysis of Gains through frequency distribution. The Analysis of Gains was used to measure the difference between the CRLA-BoSY (Pre-test) and CRLA-MoSY (Post-test) scores obtained from the measurement instrument. In solving the gains, the difference was calculated by subtracting the result of the CRLA-BoSY from the result of the CRLA-MoSY.

On the other hand, the Thematic Analysis was used to determine the views of the participants to the approach used to address the

reading difficulties they experienced. Thematic Analysis is a method of analyzing data applied to a set of text such as interview transcripts. The researchers closely examined the data to identify the themes – topics, ideas and patterns of meaning that come up repeatedly. It was transcribed and translated without compromising the thought and content and were presented by its English translations.

Results and Discussion

Part I

Figure 1. Reading Performance of One Hundred Ninety-Eight (198) Struggling Readers Before the Implementation of READology Approach (Pre- Assessment)

The first figure reveals the result of Beginning of the School Year Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment. It shows the number of reading proficiency level of the pupils’ grades 1 to 3. In grade 1-3, the number of assessed pupils in Magindanawn is 198. Out of which, 120 pupils are under Full Refreshers, 51 pupils are Moderate Refreshers, 16 pupils are Light Refreshers and 11 are Grade Ready.

In grade 2-3 Filipino, out of 121 pupils assessed, 78 pupils are under Full Refreshers, 27 are in Moderate Refreshers, 6 are in Light Refreshers and 10 are in Grade Ready. While in grade 3 English, out of 65 pupils assessed. There are 50 pupils fall under Full Refreshers, 11 are under Moderate Refreshers, 1 are Light Refreshers and 3 are Grade Ready in English.

Thus, Grade 1-3 learners have the greatest number of non-readers in the subject Magindanawn. On the contrary, Filipino has the least number of non-readers. They must be given the more focus in the intervention. Further, it concluded that the Grade 1-3 Magindanawn students are the most Grade Ready class.

Part II

Figure 2. Reading Performance of One Hundred Ninety-Eight (198) Struggling Readers After the Implementation of READology Approach (Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment Result- Middle of the School Year)

The second figure reflects the result of Middle of the School Year Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment. There are 198 enrollees who are assessed from Grades One to Three.

In grade 1-3, 198 pupils are assessed in Magindanawn, 53 (27%) of which are under Full Refreshers, another 55 (28%) are in Moderate Refreshers, 34 (17%) are in Light Refreshers and 56 (28%) are Grade Ready. In grade 2-3 Filipino, 121 pupils are assessed. 34 (28%) pupils are Full Refreshers, 29 (24%) are Moderate Refreshers, 26 (21%) are Light Refreshers, and 32 (26%) are Grade Ready.

While in English 3, out of 65 assessed, there are 30 (46%) pupils under Full Refreshers, 15 (23%) are Moderate Refreshers, 13 (20%) are Light Refreshers, and 7 (11%) are Grade Ready.

Thus, Grade 3 learners have the lowest number of full-refresher in the subject English with a 46% and is followed by Grade 1-3 Magindanawn with 27%.

On the contrary, Grade 1-3 Magindanawn increases for Grade Ready for 28% while Grade 2-3 Filipino get the second highest percentage of Grade Ready as 26%. Moreover, English 3 receives the lowest for Grade Ready with 11% and must be given more focus in the intervention.

Part III

Table 1. Difference in the reading proficiency levels of one hundred ninety-eight (198) non-readers before and after the implementation of READology Approach

Grade	Language	No. of Learners		No. of Learners		Full Refresher	G A	Moderate Refresher	G A	Light Refresher	G A	Grade Ready	G A				
		Enrolled		Assessed													
		BoS	Mo SY	BoS	Mo SY												
Grade 1 to 3	Magindanawn	198	198	198	198	120	53	67	51	55	4	16	34	18	11	56	45
Grade 2 to 3	Filipino	121	121	121	121	78	34	44	27	29	2	6	26	20	10	32	22
Grade 3	English	65	65	65	65	50	30	20	11	15	4	1	13	12	2	6	4

Table 1 shows the significant gains in the performance of the learners after the conduct of BoSY and MoSY. From 120 respondents during the BoSY, the learners who belongs to Full Refresher decreased to 53, while Filipino, from 78 decreased to 34, moreover, in English, from 50 decreased to 30. For Moderate Refresher, from 51 respondents of Magindanawn during the CRLA-BoSY (Pre-Test), the learners who belongs to moderate refresher increased to 55. In Filipino, from 27 increase to 29, while in English, from 11 increases to 18. In Light Refresher, from 16 respondents during the CRLA-BoSY (Pre-Test), the learners who belongs to light refresher increased to 34. In Filipino, from 6 respondents increased to 26, while English, from 1 respondent increased to 13. For Grade Ready, it significantly shows the increase of respondents in Grade Ready, from 11 evidently increased to 56 for Magindanawn, In Filipino, from 10 increased to 32, while in English, from 2 increased to 6.

The table also presents significant gains in Full Refresher of 67 (34%) in Magindanawn, 44 (36%) in Filipino, and 20 (31%) in English.

For Moderate Refresher, there are 4 (2%) gain in Magindanawn, 2 (2%) in Filipino, and 4 (6%) in English.

In Light Refresher, there is a significant gain of 18 (9%) in Magindanawn, 20 (17%) in Filipino, and 12 (18%) in English.

And for the Grade Ready, there are 45 (23%) gains in Magindanawn, 22 (18%) in Filipino ,and 4 (6%) in English. The difference and gains indicate that there is an improvement in the performance of the respondents during the CRLA-MoSY (Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment Result- Middle of the School Year). The result further implies that READology as an intervention is effective.

Part IV

Interventions Applied by the Researchers in the Difficulties of reading Encountered by Non-readers of Buaya Buaya Elementary School

The results of pre-test, post-test and gains in the performance of the Non-readers after the implementation of the intervention was discussed in tables one (1), two (2) and three (3).

On this section, the researcher analysed the data gathered from the interview conducted to the respondents to describe how READology as an approach addressed the reading difficulties experienced by the learners.

All respondents believed that READology helped them address their reading difficulties and improved their reading abilities.It was presented in textual or descriptive form. It included the themes and thematic statements.

Make Reading Easy

This theme shows that teachers repeating letters, syllables, and words until they read them better would help them read faster and easier. Readology aids struggling readers. These strategies simplify reading for non-readers in numerous ways. Readology helps non-readers learn phonemic awareness and word decoding through syllable, letter, and word repetition.

Respondent 1: “it speeded up and helped my reading ability”

Respondent 6,8,12: “I used to not know the alphabet, because of this, I learned to spell words”

Respondent 2,11: “it helps me to facilitate my reading skills”

Respondent 7,9: “ I learned to read because my teacher repeatedly teach me how to read letter, syllables, and words”

Respondent 3: “I can read now the words unlike before I did not read any”

Familiarize Letter Name and Sound.

Teachers utilize this strategy to help pupils remember, identify, read, and no longer mistake letter names and sounds. Reading and recognizing letters is essential to literacy. This foundational knowledge helps non-readers connect letters, sounds, and words for reading comprehension and fluency. Without this information, non-readers may struggle to interpret words and read. By focusing on letter-sound identification, non-readers may acquire word sounds and letters.

Respondents 1,5,6,15: “I knew and memorized now the sound of the letters, and I am now not confused on the sound of the letters”

Respondent 2, 3,10: “ I learned to identify the different sound of the letters”

Respondent 7,11,12,13: “It helps me a lot to know and recognize the name of the letters”

Respondent 8,9,10,14,: “ I can identify and read the first letter, I can read easily syllables from words, and now I can read fast the syllables and words ”

Build confidence in writing

This theme shows that READology Approach may build confident to learners in their writing skills. Teachers feel that pupils' work improves with better writing. Feedback may be crucial to students' writing confidence. Writing styles impact students' confidence and competence. Teachers must examine pupils' writing skills to help them achieve (Murphy, 2021).

Respondent 1: “I really learned to write words, they no longer make fun of me for not being able to read”

Respondent 2: “my mother was surprised because I can spell a word now”

Respondent 3: “ I learned and can now spell a word”

Respondent 4: “I can write a word about the picture that is visible and I can spell words as Well”

Respondent 5: “I got better at spelling, I learned more and I always raise my hand to answer and read in class”

Respondent 14: “I learned to spell words”

Respondent 15: “I learned to read and spell words”

Respondent 13: “I learned to spell words”

Respondent 12: “I like reading because even if I read poorly I can participate”

Effective Game-Based Learning

It is becoming clear that standard teaching approaches may not work for all students, especially those who struggle with reading. Activity-based learning may help non-readers improve their reading skills (Harper, 2021). As a result, active, meaningful learning may be presented to non-readers as an alternate educational technique. This technique exposed students to advanced vocabulary and grammatical structures (Al-Shammari & Ahmed, 2019).

Respondent 1: “I love it because it's like we're just playing”

Respondent 3: “it's fun, it's like we're just playing”

Respondent 15: “we have fun playing and learning”

Respondent 12: “it's fun because it's like we're just playing”

Respondent 4: “I got better from reading while we were playing, I like it as if we were just playing”

Respondent 5: “Magic box reading became a game for my siblings and I at home”

Respondent 13: “I love it because there is always a contest in the classroom, we are competing as well who will go first

Respondent 11: “I'm happy because while I'm playing, I've learned to read”

Images: Build Reading and Writing

This theme points out the importance of images in teaching reading. Visual media in the curriculum encourages active learning, critical thinking, cooperation, teamwork, global communication, and media expertise (Alfailakawi & Al-Anzi, 2023). Visual literacy theory may teach pupils visual reading, writing, thinking, learning, and other abilities. Interactive teaching approaches like photography may boost students' creativity and independence.

Respondent 3: "Even though I don't know how to read, I can say what is in the picture."

Respondent 6: "I can Find out the first and last letter of the picture when there is a picture shown."

Respondent 8: "I can identify the letter by showing the picture"

Respondent 9 "I know the name of the picture"

Respondent 11: "words can be read faster because of the picture/ I like because there is a picture that becomes our guide"

Respondent 12: "it helps because there is a picture"

Respondent 1: "I love the pictures"

Respondent 13: "because of the picture I can remember it easily"

Respondent 14: "the word can be read faster because there is a picture./it helped that I can easily remember the word"

Respondent 15: "the word can be read and remembered faster because of the picture"

Building Friends and Care with Parents

This theme presents the application of the approach give and build strong relationships with their classmates and parents. Reading with parents helps create a pleasant learning environment for children. Reading together fosters language development, literacy, and a love of reading while strengthening parent-child bonds. According to study, children's reading aptitude generally resembles their parents' literacy (Rahmawati et al., 2022). Schools may improve academic performance by encouraging parents to read to their children (Gándara et al., 2003).

Respondent 2: "they want to be friends with me and join the activity"

Respondent 5: "I imitate it at home with my brothers"

Respondent 10: "I always participate in reading and my classmates don't laugh at me anymore"

Respondent 2: "My mother doesn't scold me anymore, she even taught me to read"

Respondent 3: "My mother always buys me reading materials"

Respondent 7: "My mother always asked me if I could read because she would buy me anything I wanted"

Respondent 10: "my mother always let me go to school for reading"

Conclusions

The teacher's responsibility commences upon entering the classroom and continues until she departs. Each academic year, a consistent issue emerges in every classroom, requiring instructors to address and implement interventions for.

The finding from the result shows how effective the intervention applied by the teachers. The decrease of full refreshers and the high increase of light refreshers and grade ready are manifestation that the five or six months of conducting everyday reading sessions and series of reading tutorials were not failed.

This year is more difficult for educators to manage due to the fact that instruction must be conducted outside of the classroom, and students with literacy difficulties must be addressed in a more complex manner. Teachers must strengthen and maintain communication and partnerships with parents in order to receive their support as we educate their children. It is imperative that we evaluate not only the students' but also the parents' abilities in order to ascertain the students' strengths and weaknesses and obtain information on how to develop an intervention strategy. Prior to the adoption of READology as a remedial strategy for reading difficulties, 198 students were experiencing reading difficulties. A considerable decline in the proportion of students who encountered difficulties with reading was observed subsequent to the execution of the intervention and the results of the interview showed that READology simplifies reading, provides learners with letter names and sounds, Promotes learners' confidence, creates an efficient Game-Based learning environment, aids in the development of reading and writing skills through visuals, and fosters love and compassion between learners and their parents.

The findings of this study indicated that the children's performance improved following the implementation of the intervention. As a result, the researchers advise that the intervention be replicated with additional groups of Non-reader learners. Notwithstanding this, divergent findings might be perceived by a broader group on account of the study's limited sample size. Additionally, the researchers advise that the study be replicated on a larger group.

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